

factsheet 01

Methodology for the analysis of practices

Introduction

This factsheet outlines the methodology used by National B-THENET Centres to evaluate the best beekeeping practices that beekeepers identified as priority in the EU.

Overview

The analysis was carried out on the basis of the following criteria:

Sustainability, including:

- Economic value
- Human health
- Bee health
- Environmental protection

02. Scientific value

03. Readiness-to-use

The National B-THENET Centres could assign a rating ranging from zero to three stars for each criterion.

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Zero Stars

The practices' overall rating was calculated as a weighted sum of stars for the different criteria considered.

Elaboration on the Criteria

01 Sustainability

Sustainable beekeeping refers to all activities concerned with the practical management of social bee species that are capable of continuing over time, causing little or no negative impacts to humans, animals, and the environment.

To evaluate **Sustainability** of the best beekeeping practices the following points were considered:

- **Cost-benefit (of production and hive products)**
 - Economic value of the practice was evaluated taking into account costs of the materials and time needed to apply it, as well as the economic gains deriving from its application.
- **Bee health**
- **Human Health (Beekeepers & Consumers)**
- **Environmental protection**

02 Scientific Value

The preservation and promotion of certain qualities or features which have scientific significance.

Users could define this value by citing scientific (or grey but reasonable literature) papers.

03 Readiness-to-use

We define "readiness-to-use" as practices that can be dispensed with minimal or no effort in terms of beekeepers' knowledge and the tools/equipment required.

Users could determine this value by providing evidence from journal articles or other sources. Additionally, the "limited" use of a practice may be linked to specific characteristics of the practice, such as the availability of particular tools that are not easily found or widely distributed in the country or area.

Conclusion

B-THENET project partners, in collaboration with collaborating partners, will evaluate and rate each practice individually through exchange activities with beekeepers and advisors with the aim of discussing practices both theoretically and on-field at the apiary level.

At LOCAL level	At EU level
13 National B-THENET Centres	3 International B-THENET Centres representing
National B-THENET Centre Austria	EU Beekeepers
National B-THENET Centre Belgium	Advisers
National B-THENET Centre Croatia	Other Stakeholders
National B-THENET Centre Denmark	
National B-THENET Centre Germany	
National B-THENET Centre Greece	
National B-THENET Centre Hungary	
National B-THENET Centre Italy	
National B-THENET Centre Poland	
National B-THENET Centre Slovakia	
National B-THENET Centre Slovenia	
National B-THENET Centre Spain	
National B-THENET Centre Sweden	

After conducting a specific sociological study, only the top-scoring best practices from the analysis will be developed and published on the Exchange Platform in the local language.

Disclaimer: If required, the methodology will be revised during the course of the project.

What is B-THENET?

B-THENET is the first EU thematic network for sustainable beekeeping.

B-THENET brings together different actors and their expertise to co-create and share knowledge to find applicable solutions for EU beekeepers.

Join our Network

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Our consortium

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